

ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' LEVEL OF INTEREST IN MATHEMATICS AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of interest in Mathematics and the academic performance of Junior High School students in Mathematics. It used the correlational research design whose primary goal is to determine the relationship between the respondents' interest in mathematics and performance in Mathematics. The method used in conducting this study is the descriptive survey method with the use of data from school records and adopted questionnaires. There were 263 respondents in the study. They were Junior High School students from Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan. Four statistical treatments were used in this study: percentage, weighted mean, mean, and Pearson R Correlation. It was revealed that most of the respondents who participated in the study were female. In terms of year level, grade 10 has the most participants with 69 respondents. Results showed that the respondents were moderately interested in Mathematics. Concerning their academic performance, it was very satisfactory. It was found that there is a low positive correlation of 0.324 between the respondents' level of interest and academic performance in Mathematics. It was concluded that there is a significant relationship between the student's level of interest in Mathematics and their academic performance in Mathematics, although not strongly. This implies that students' interest in Mathematics can affect their academic performance in the subject area, although not entirely. This further implies that while interest appeared to be a significant predictor of the student's academic performance, it can also be concluded that there could be other factors that would also affect the student's academic performance.

Keywords: *Level of Interest in Mathematics, Academic Performance, Junior High School Students, Performance in Mathematics, Mathematics Enjoyment, Motivation Towards Learning Mathematics*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a discipline that is omnipresent in our day-to-day basis. Knowingly and unknowingly, it is applied in various fields to solve problems as well as to predict outcomes. In the present scenario, mathematics is a necessary subject for a better living of the individual.

In education, Mathematics is one of the most established disciplines and is part of the curriculum around the world. Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (2015), states that one of the goals of the primary mathematics curriculum is to stimulate interest in the learning of mathematics. The same goes for the secondary mathematics curriculum which is to help students develop a positive attitude toward mathematics and the ability to appreciate the aesthetic nature and the cultural aspects of mathematics.

However, the framework of the Mathematics curriculum made the conduct of learning seem to be a vigorous process. Although it is a valuable subject, it is also very challenging. In this view, students started to embrace the stigma that the subject is only for the exceptional ones. While some may find it interestingly facile, one sits alone on the side and struggles to understand the concept and/or solve the assigned problems. Some students even learned a negative connotation that at its complexity, learning Mathematics became irrelevant—a static corpus of knowledge that is theoretical and not practical. Even those who perform well in school can't see the point of spending so much school time studying the subject anymore. Consequently, students developed negative attitudes towards mathematics and became reluctant to learn it.

As widely believed, interest has a vital role in learning mathematics (Yu & Singh, 2016). Sauer (2012) found that students' interest in learning is one of the contributing factors to successful academic performance. In contrast, Yu and Singh (2016) reported an unanticipated result that showed that the relationship between interest and mathematics performance was insignificant.

Given these inconclusive results, this research aims to explore if the level of interest in learning Mathematics is related to the academic performance among the Junior High School students at Guihulngan National High School- Hilaitan.

This research is designed to determine if a strong interest in Mathematics is closely related to excellent grades in the subject area and if a decline in interest in Mathematics is closely related to lower grades in the subject area.

Research Questions

The objective of this study is to explore the relationship between the interest and academic performance in Mathematics of Junior High School students in Guihulngan National High School – Hilaitan. Specifically, the following research questions will be answered:

1. What is the respondents' profile in terms of:
 - 1.1. gender; and
 - 1.2. year level?
2. What is the respondents' level of interest in learning Mathematics?
3. What is the respondents' academic performance in Mathematics?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of interest in learning Mathematics and their academic performance?

Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between students' interest in mathematics and their academic performance.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The researcher used a descriptive-correlational research design. The correlational research design used for the association between two variables was investigated and the method used in conducting this study is the descriptive survey method. The researchers used an adopted questionnaire to collect necessary data about students' level of interest in learning Mathematics and referred to the school records for the student's academic performance.

Environment

This study was conducted around the premises of Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan where survey questionnaires were administered to two hundred sixty-three (263) Junior High School students. GNHS-Hilaitan is a suburban public school located at Brgy. Hilaitan, Guihulngan City, Negros Occidental, Philippines adjacent to Hilaitan Elementary School. This school has a total population of 1,168 students from both Junior and Senior high school levels.

Respondents

A total of two-hundred sixty-three (263) Junior High School students at Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan were chosen to be the respondents of this study. Sixty-six (66) of them are from grade 7, other sixty-six (66) are from grade 8, sixty-two (62) are grade 9 students, and sixty-nine (69) are grade 10 students. For the selection of

respondents, the researchers utilized a stratified random sampling technique where sample size from the entire population is taken using Slovin's formula

Instrument

The researchers adapted the Mathematics Interest Inventory (MII) as the instrument of the study. These twenty-seven (27) items questionnaire was developed by Tara Stevens and Arturo Olivarez. The researchers only added a few questions such as the profile of the respondents including their gender and year level, and their academic performance.

Data Gathering Procedure

The gathering of data was made possible by asking permission from the office of the principal at Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan to conduct research in the said school. After the request has been approved, the researchers then administer the questionnaire onsite to gather the data needed from the chosen respondents (Junior High School students). Students were asked to provide a few personal details such as gender and year level as well as their current grades in Mathematics. For the MII items, students were asked to rate how similar they were to the descriptions using a five-point Likert scale.

Treatment of Data

The researcher used the percentage to determine the profile of the students. To determine the student's level of interest in mathematics performance of the students and the extent of student's academic performance, a weighted mean was used. The researcher also used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the significant relationship between students' level of interest in learning mathematics and the academic performance of the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Demographic profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the demographic profile of the respondents (n= 263)

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	124	47
Female	139	53
Year Level		
7	66	25
8	66	25
9	62	24
10	69	26

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. As revealed, 53 percent or 139 out of 263 respondents of this study were female and the other 124 which comprised 47 percent were male. This analysis implies that the majority of the respondents who participated and responded to the questionnaire of this study were female. This implies that female students outnumbered the male ones. The findings are in agreement with the report of the 2020 Global Gender Gap Report of the World Economic Forum (WEF) which states that Filipino women are enrolled in high school and college is significantly higher rates than men. WEF found that 71.3 percent of women are enrolled in secondary education and 40.4 percent in college, compared to only 60.2 percent and 40.4 percent, respectively, among men. On the other hand, for the year level, it shows that 69 or 26 percent of the respondents of this study were composed of grade 10 students in Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan. Sixty-six or 25 percent were from grade 7 and other 66 were grade 8 students; while there are only 62 or 24 percent respondents from grade 9.

2. Level of Interest in Mathematics

This section presented the respondents' level of interest in mathematics. The data gathered was presented in tabular form where the weighted mean of each indicator or statement was included as well as each corresponding verbal description.

Table 2. Level of Interest of the Respondents towards Learning Mathematics

1. S/N	2. Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1.	I like to answer questions in mathematics class.	3.51	High Level
2.	I like mathematics.	3.46	High Level
3.	I am interested in mathematics.	3.52	High Level
4.	Knowing a lot about mathematics is helpful.	3.77	High Level
5.	I feel happy when it comes to working on mathematics.	3.49	High Level
6.	I work to know all about how to do mathematics problem.	3.32	Moderate Level
7.	I am excited when a new mathematics topic is announced.	3.50	High Level
8.	I want to learn more about mathematics.	3.92	High Level
9.	I choose to work on mathematics.	3.26	Moderate Level
10.	I want to know all about mathematics.	3.68	High Level
11.	I am wasting my time on mathematics.	2.71	Moderate Level
12.	I am bored when working on mathematics.	2.66	Moderate Level
13.	I would rather be working be working on something else besides math.	3.07	Moderate Level
14.	I give up easily when working on mathematics.	2.70	Moderate Level

15. When working on mathematics I want to stop and start working on something else.	2.70	Moderate Level
16. I am always thinking of other things when working on mathematics.	2.99	Moderate Level
17. I get mad easily when working on mathematics.	2.73	Moderate Level
18. I have difficulty paying attention when working on mathematics.	3.75	High Level
19. I spend a little time as possible working on math.	3.12	Moderate Level
20. I struggle with Mathematics.	3.87	High Level
21. I work more mathematics problems than I have to.	3.24	Moderate Level
22. I spend many hours working on math.	3.00	Moderate Level
23. I work on math in my spare time.	3.04	Moderate Level
24. I want to talk about math with my friends.	3.39	Moderate Level
25. I spend more time than my classmates working on math.	3.16	Moderate Level
26. I prefer easy mathematics over mathematics that is hard.	3.68	High Level
27. I am too involved in mathematics.	3.39	Moderate Level
Overall Weighted Mean	3.28	Moderate Level

Table 2 shows that the respondents agree on the positively worded statements specifically item numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, and 10. They find these items that express their interest in Mathematics true to themselves. The said items also revealed that the respondents are eager to learn all about Mathematics and that they are excited to work on problems related to it because they believe that knowing more about it is helpful.

Furthermore, the respondents also agree on the negatively worded statements which are numbers 18, 20, and 26. These items convey that the respondents prefer easy topics in Mathematics over those that are hard because they are struggling in this subject and that they have difficulty paying attention when working on it. Mazana et al. (2019) reported factors associated with low achievement in mathematics, and these include students' attitudes toward mathematics and the perception that the subject is complex.

The respondents remained undecided on 16 out of 27 statements describing their interest in learning Mathematics. Overall, the aggregated weighted mean is 3.28 which implies that the Junior High School respondents from Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan are moderately interested in Mathematics. Sauer (2012) found in his study that students' interest in learning is one of the contributing factors to successful academic performance.

3. Academic Performance

This section concerns the academic performance of the respondents. The respondents' academic performance was categorized into five (5) where each category has its corresponding scale range and verbal description. The data gathered was presented in tabular form.

Table 3. The Academic Performance of the Respondents in Mathematics

Verbal Description	Scale Range	f	%
Outstanding	90-100	53	20.15
Very Satisfactory	85-89	91	34.60
Satisfactory	80-84	97	36.88
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	22	8.37
Poor	Below 75	0	0
Total		263	100
Mean			85.42
Verbal Description			Very Satisfactory

Table 3 above shows that 97 out of 263 respondents from Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan, 36.88 percent, have satisfactory academic performance in Mathematics. Ninety-one, or 34.60 percent, have very satisfactory academic performance, while 20.15 percent, or 53, have outstanding academic performance.

Moreover, 22 respondents, or 8.37 percent have fairly satisfactory academic performance and none of them performed poorly in the subject area. Overall, the respondents from Guihulngan National High School- Hilaitan have very satisfactory academic performance in Mathematics with a mean of 85.42. This is in contradiction to Peteros et al. (2020) report which states that in the Philippines, the level of performance in mathematics in 2020 was low as the majority of students (53.01%) performed below the average.

4. Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Interest in Mathematics and their Academic Performance in Mathematics

Table 4.

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	Decision	Result
Level of Interest in Mathematics and Academic Performance	0.324	Low Correlation	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 4 reflects the test on significant relationship between the Level of Interest in Mathematics and Academic Performance of the respondents. Using the Pearson R Correlation test, the result shows a correlation coefficient r-value of 0.324. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between the Level of Interest in Mathematics and Academic Performance of the respondents from Guihulungan National High School-Hilaitan. The null hypothesis, therefore, is rejected.

The Pearson r-value is 0.324, by which, referring to the classifications indicated to interpret the correlation value implies a low positive correlation. This revealed that the level of interest in mathematics can affect the academic performance of the Junior High School respondents from Guihulungan National High School- Hilaitan but not strongly. This implies that students' interest in Mathematics may be a significant predictor of their academic performance in the subject area, although not entirely. This result is in agreement to the study of Puracan et al. (2023) where findings show that the interest of the Asian College of Technology respondents in mathematics can predict their academic performance in General Mathematics although not strongly. Student performance, in general, is affected by many factors which includes student' learning skills, parental background, peer influence, competence of teacher, and learning environment (Briones, et al., 2021).

It is noted in Tables 3.0 and 4.0 that the respondents' level of interest in Mathematics is moderate yet their academic performance is very satisfactory. These results imply that despite having lower interest in Mathematics, students could still perform well in the subject area as they were driven to learn because of some other factors. These findings are supported by Wong and Wong (2019), the students, despite having lower level of interest towards mathematics, could still perform better in mathematics test because they were driven to learn for extrinsic reasons like avoiding negative consequences from not performing well and that their learning activities in the classroom were more structured. Yu and Singh (2016) argued the reciprocal effects like personal variables (self-efficacy) and classroom practice may be the reasons that interest is not a direct predictor of mathematics performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers derived with a conclusion that the level of interest in Mathematics is significantly related to the academic performance in the said subject area. However, the strength of correlation appeared low or weak positive which implies that the level of interest in Mathematics among the Junior High School students in Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan can significantly affect their academic performance in Mathematics, but not strongly. This further implies that while interest appeared to be a significant predictor of the students' academic performance, it can be concluded that there could be other factors that would also affect the students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions derived in this study, the researchers were able to formulate the following recommendations. To increase the students' level of interest and academic performance in Mathematics, teachers have more work to do. Thereafter, the students should be exposed in a classroom setting where learning Mathematics is not a vigorous process but an interactive, engaging, and fun undertaking. Teachers can implement a peer learning programs where students in a high Mathematics performance group help those who are in a low Mathematics performance group. This will allow students share knowledge in a more comfortable manner so their mathematics skills will improve. Furthermore, regular faculty meetings, peer evaluation of matching competencies, curriculum development seminars and colleague mentoring can also be conducted to enable the teachers to be more equipped in teaching the subject. It appeared in this paper that there could be other predictor of the students' academic performance. With this, the researchers would like to recommend for further studies where future researchers will use other factors which may affect the students' academic performance in Mathematics such as teaching strategies employed during the instruction, teacher competency, students' self-efficacy, and even environment and school facilities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To uphold the rights and welfare of the participants involved in the conduct of this study, the researchers are taking full responsibility for protecting them from any risk or harm associated with their participation for the success of this academic pursuit. To do this so, they adhere to the following ethical management practices:

- Confidentiality. The collected insights from the respondents will be treated with utmost confidentiality; hence, they will be kept private and will be used for academic purposes only.
- Informed Consent. Before data collection, permission was asked from the office of the principal at GNHS-Hilaitan. Upon approval, respondents were given detailed information about the study's objectives and process. Respondents were assured of their voluntary participation.

By adhering to these ethical guidelines, researchers ensured the validity and reliability of their findings while prioritizing the rights and welfare of respondents.

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